

Table S1 Primers and probes (P) used in PCR reactions and references [numbers in bold] where specific conditions of the PCR reactions are described

Organism Gene	Primers and probes (P)	Sequences (5'-3')	Refs.
<i>A. phagocytophilum</i> <i>msp2</i>	ApMSP2f ApMSP2r ApMSP2p (P)	ATGGAAGGTAGTGTGGTTATGGTATT TTGGTCTTGAAGCGCTCGTA HEX-TGGTGCCAGGGTTGAGCTTGAGATTG-TAMRA	[1, 2]
<i>A. phagocytophilum</i> 16S rRNA	1 st amplification: ge3a ge10r 2 nd amplification: ge9f ge2	CACATGCAAGTCGAACGGATTATTC TTCCGTAAAGAAGGATCTAATCTCC AACGGATTATTCTTTATAGCTTGCT GGCAGTATTAAGCAGCTCCAGG	[3, 4]
<i>A. phagocytophilum</i> <i>groEL</i>	EphplgroEL-A.phago-F EphgroEL-A.phago-R	ATGGTATGCAGTTTGATCGC TTGAGTACAGCAACACCACCGAA	[5, 6] ^a
<i>Cand. N. mikurensis</i> <i>groEL</i>	NMikGroEL-F2 NMikGroEL rev1 NMikGroEL rev2 NMikGroEL-P2a (P)	CCTTGAAAATATAGCAAGATCAGGTAG CCACCACGTAACCTATTTAGCACTAAAG CCACCACGTAACCTATTTAGTACTAAAG FAM-CCTCTACTAATTATTGCTGAAGATGTAGAAGGTGAAGC-BHQ1	[7, 8, 9]
<i>C. burnetii</i> <i>com1</i>	CBCOS CBCOE	GCTGTTTCTGCCGAACGTAT AGACAACGCGGAGGTTTTTA	[10]
<i>B. burgdorferi</i> s.l. 5S-23S (rrfA-rrlB) intergenic spacer	IgsA IgsB	CGACCTTCTTCGCCTTAAAGC AGCTCTTATTCGCTGATGGTA	[11]
<i>Rickettsia</i> sp. <i>gltA</i>	RPCS877 RPCS1258	GGGGACCTGCTCACGGCGG ATTGCAAAAAGTACAGTGAACA	[12, 13]
<i>Babesia</i> sp./ <i>Theileria</i> sp. 18S rRNA	BJ1 BN2	GTCTTGTAATTGGAATGATGG TAGTTTATGGTTAGGACTACG	[14, 15]
18S rRNA (qPCR)	Bab_18SrRNA-F Bab_18SrRNA-R Bab_18SrRNA-P (P)	CAGCTTGACGGTAGGGTATTGG TCGAACCCTAATTCCCCGTTA 6-FAM CGAGGCAGCAACGG-MGB	[16] ^b
ITS (qPCR)	Bmicr_ITS_F Bmicr_ITS_R Bmicr_ITS_px1 (P)	CTCACACAACGATGAAGGACGCA AACAGAGGCAGTGTGTACAATACATTCAGA HEX-GCA +GAATTTAG+CAAAT+CAACAGG-TAMRA	This study ^c

MGB, minor groove binder group; +, Locked Nucleic Acid; BHQ, Black Hole Quencer.

If not specified otherwise, DNA lysates from questing *I. ricinus* ticks in which presence of the tested microorganisms was confirmed by PCR and sequencing served as positive controls.

^a The positive control for *A. phagocytophilum* (q)PCRs is a DNA lysate of a spleen from a roe deer positive for *A. phagocytophilum* [6].

^b The positive control for the *Babesia* sp. (q)PCRs is a DNA lysate of a spleen from a captive reindeer positive for *Babesia capreoli* [17].

^c The positive control for the *B. microti* (q)PCR is a DNA lysate of a spleen from a rodent positive for *Babesia microti* (unpublished).

The multiplex qPCR for the simultaneous detection of *Cand. N. mikurensis* and *A. phagocytophilum* as well as the qPCR for *Babesia* sp. were performed using the 2x IQ-powermix (Bio-rad, Veenendaal, Netherlands) under the following conditions: 5 min 95°C, then 60 cycles of 5 s 94°C, 35 s 60°C and ending by 20 s 37°C.

Detailed protocols for the qPCR are available upon request.

References to Table S1.

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Table S2 GenBank accession numbers of *A. phagocytophilum* 16S rRNA and *groEL* gene sequences identified in spleen and engorged ticks from free-living ungulates

Name of the isolate	Source	bp	GenBank accession number	
			16S rRNA	<i>groEl</i>
18SPZ ^a	<i>Capreolus capreolus</i> spleen	530		MF061229
55SPZ	<i>Capreolus capreolus</i> spleen	530		MF061230
19SPZ	<i>Cervus elaphus</i> spleen	530		MF061231
21SPZ	<i>Cervus elaphus</i> spleen	530		MF061232
51SPZ	<i>Dama dama</i> spleen	530		MF061233
25SPZ	<i>Dama dama</i> spleen	530		MF061234
10SPZ	<i>Ovis musimon</i> spleen	530		MF061235
10SPZ	<i>Ovis musimon</i> spleen	497	MF061301	
63SPZ	<i>Ovis musimon</i> spleen	530		MF061236
13SPZ	<i>Sus scrofa</i> spleen	530		MF061237
43SPZ	<i>Sus scrofa</i> spleen	530		MF061238
129KPZ ^b	<i>Ixodes ricinus</i> larva from <i>D. dama</i>	530		MG773209
158KPZ	<i>I. ricinus</i> larva from <i>D. dama</i>	530		MG773210

^a SPZ, spleen from game; ^b KPZ, ticks from game

Table S3 GenBank accession numbers of piroplasmid 18S rRNA gene sequences identified in spleen of free-living ungulates and engorged ticks

Name of the isolate	Source (number of analysed samples with identical sequences)	Species	bp	GenBank accession number
1SPZ ^a	<i>Capreolus capreolus</i> spleen (11)	<i>Theileria</i> sp. 1	467	KX470610
52SPZ	<i>Cervus elaphus</i> spleen (3)	<i>Theileria</i> sp. 2	467	KX470611
87SPZ	<i>Dama dama</i> spleen (18)	<i>Theileria</i> sp. 2	467	KX470612
21KPZ ^b	<i>Ixodes ricinus</i> larva attached to <i>C. capreolus</i> (5)	<i>Theileria</i> sp. 1	467	KX470613
188KPZ	<i>I. ricinus</i> nymph attached to <i>C. capreolus</i> (6)	<i>Theileria</i> sp. 1	467	KX470614
1KPZ	<i>I. ricinus</i> female attached to <i>C. capreolus</i> (2)	<i>Theileria</i> sp. 1	467	KX470615
312KPZ	<i>Haemaphysalis concinna</i> nymph attached to <i>C. capreolus</i> (3)	<i>Theileria</i> sp. 1	467	KX470616
48KPZ	<i>I. ricinus</i> larva attached to <i>C. elaphus</i> (1)	<i>Theileria</i> sp. 2	467	KX470617
45KPZ	<i>I. ricinus</i> nymph attached to <i>C. elaphus</i> (1)	<i>Theileria</i> sp. 2	467	KX470618
59KPZ	<i>I. ricinus</i> female attached to <i>C. elaphus</i> (3)	<i>Theileria</i> sp. 2	467	KX470619
132KPZ	<i>I. ricinus</i> larva attached to <i>D. dama</i> (9)	<i>Theileria</i> sp. 2	467	KX470620
71KPZ	<i>I. ricinus</i> nymph attached to <i>D. dama</i> (9)	<i>Theileria</i> sp. 2	467	KX470621
390KPZ	<i>I. ricinus</i> female attached to <i>D. dama</i> (12)	<i>Theileria</i> sp. 2	467	KX470622
139KPZ	<i>I. ricinus</i> male attached to <i>D. dama</i> (2)	<i>Theileria</i> sp. 2	467	KX470623
299KPZ	<i>I. ricinus</i> larva attached to <i>C. capreolus</i> (3)	<i>Babesia</i> <i>venatorum</i>	447	KX470624
376KPZ	<i>I. ricinus</i> female attached to <i>D. dama</i> (1)	<i>Babesia</i> <i>venatorum</i>	447	KX470625
306KPZ	<i>H. concinna</i> larva attached to <i>C. capreolus</i> (2)	<i>Babesia</i> sp.	432	KX470626

^a SPZ, spleen from game; ^b KPZ, ticks from game